

Work done by Time is equal to Einstein's Mass-Energy Equivalence

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Abstract: The ability to do some work is energy. Work is done when a force is applied to an object and energy is the ability to do some work on the object. This paper discusses work and its energy and also shows that the work done by time is equal to Einstein's mass-energy equivalence.

Keywords: force, displacement, mass, speed of light

1. Introduction

The equation of Einstein's mass-energy equivalence [1-7] is $E = mc^2$, where E, m, and c denote energy, mass, and speed of light respectively. The derivation of the equations of mass-energy equivalence is obtained from the work done by time.

2. Work and Mass-Energy Equivalence

Force (F) is an action that tends to maintain the motion of a particle with mass m.

$$F = m \times a \quad (1)$$

Work done on a particle is defined as the product of magnitude of displacement and the component of force in the direction of displacement.

$$W = F \times s = m \times a \times s \quad (2)$$

According to Einstein's theory of special relativity, velocity of a moving particle with mass is less than the speed of light. Also, we know that the velocity of a massless particle like a photon of light is equal to the speed of light.

By substituting the acceleration $(a) = \frac{c}{t}$ and the displacement $(s) = c \times t$ in equation (2),

We get : $W = m \left(\frac{c}{t}\right) ct = mc^2$, which is equal to Einstein's mass energy equation.

Einstein's Mass-Energy Equivalence, therefore, is equal to work done by time.

3. Conclusion

In this article, the author has discussed the work and energy and also showed that the work done by time is equal to Einstein's mass-energy equivalence.

References

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